

Expropriation Procedures For Mortgaged Money "Comparative Study"

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: October 26, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: May 27, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Mortgage, Creditors, Legal</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6587758</p>	<p><i>Mortgage is considered an ancillary in-kind right, according to which the mortgagee is granted the right to reclaim his debt from the cash consideration of the mortgaged property by way ahead of the ordinary creditors and the creditors following it in rank. In this case the holder that the security mortgage is an accessory in kind right that arises from a formal contract in order to guarantee the fulfillment of a personal right through the mortgagee's enjoyment of the privilege of following the mortgaged property in any hand and the execution of it is ahead of its ordinary creditors in rank and ordinary creditors. The legal position of the holder of the mortgaged property differs from the position of the accidental holder of the mortgaged property, such as the lessee, as well as from the guarantor in kind and the inheritor. It is necessary for the Iraqi legislator to address in Article (1308/2) civil the penalty in the event of violating the procedures for releasing the mortgaged property, by arranging for the invalidity of the notification for the mortgagee creditor whose notification occurred by mistake or deficiency would have caused him harm.</i></p>

Introduction

If the immediate tracking conditions are met and the holder does not succeed in disposing of the trace by paying off the defenses to which he or she is entitled to hold the debt, the mortgaged creditor proceeds with the right to trace by expropriation of the mortgaged money by auctioning it, and the implications vary depending on the person who is the auctioneer whether he or she is the holder or others, but in both cases the holder is entitled to refer to the previous owner and debtor because of the loss suffered as a result of the execution. The Jordanian and Iraqi legislators had given the holder another opportunity whereby he could retain ownership of the mortgaged property, which in this regard had used a legal means of the right of the holder to participate in the bidding while carrying the expropriation proceedings.

Therefore, the auction procedures must be indicated and then the legal status of the holder in the event of the expropriation of the mortgaged property, so we will divide this research into two demands, allocating an independent requirement for each of the above-mentioned issues.

The first requirement Auction procedures

First: Auction procedures in Jordanian law:

The Jordanian legislator addressed this issue in the implementation law as well as in the law on the placement of immovable funds in order to secure the debt, so the researcher will indicate the position of these two laws and then indicate whether they are contrary in this regard.

The position of the Jordanian Implementation Law

The Jordanian legislator organized the implementation procedures for the property that is subject to auction in articles (70-113) of the Implementation Act, if the property is reserved for the executive case with the Department of Land and Space under article 70/a, and after the booking is made the convict is notified of a pre-sale notification of a week from the day after the date of notification, as confirmed by the text of article 70/b/4, and once the end of the week an expert is elected to hand over the property and estimate its value by an expert or More and that's what article 71 says. After the hand-holding procedure, the sale of the property is announced in a daily newspaper and a copy of the advertisement is attached to the bulletin board and on the door of the property reserved for 30 days, and the auction is entered from the day after the date of publication of the advertisement after payment of a deposit of (10%) of the value provided at the time of hand placement, as confirmed by the text of articles 83,84.

At the end of the 30-day period, the sale is temporarily referred to those in the higher allowance under article 84/b. After the temporary referral, the property is announced to be auctioned for a second time for 15 days from the day after the date of the announcement and the declaration includes the allowance for the temporary referral and the subject to which the property was referred, and the auction is entered the following day, as stipulated in article 85. In the event that the previous period (15) expires on the day of the public auctioneers, the president decides to refer the absolute transfer to the buyer who has provided the higher allowance for the text of Article

85/B.If it appears that the bid allowance is reduced by 25% and more than its estimated value, the president must re-auction the property for (30) days and once and then decide to refer the final auction for the last allowance in accordance with article 86.The definitive referral is published in one daily newspaper and on the Department's bulletin board, and the declaration includes the statement of the transferred property, the price at which it was transmitted and informing the debtor of the work of article 87.Everyone else who is not prohibited from bidding shall exceed the price within 10 days following the absolute referral bulletin with a minimum increase of (10%) of the price under Article 88/A, and the new auction will deposit an amount (10%) of the bid value at the new price, and a new bid date shall be set to exceed (15) days as stipulated in article 88/b.If several bids are made, the higher offer or the first offer is taken when the offers are equal under article 88/c.

The last sale is announced and includes the name of the offer of increase, its profession, its home, the amount of price offered in addition to the data mentioned in the first declaration and this is what article 89 required.After the end of the temporary referral period of (15) days and no one has applied, the increase (10%) will be submitted by the judge to the decision of the definitive referral to the first referral in the work of the text of article 91.The absolute referral of the debtor is notified and must be deposited in the Department's fund sufficient amount to meet the debt, fees and expenses within (15) days of the day after the decision of the absolute referral under article 92 is communicated.The shop must deposit the price in the Chamber within 10 days of the date of the definitive referral, and shall be exempted from paying the price if it is a creditor in accordance with article 94.The executioner therefore requests that the decision of the absolute referral be registered after the payment of the price and expenses under article 95, and if the person referred to him does not meet the obligations contained in the previous item, he is notified of the need to meet the price within 30 days if he does not meet the price, during the period the President decides to resell the property and specifies the date of the hearing at which the sale takes place, and the sale must take place no later than (15) days after the decision is issued in accordance with article 96.The decision to resell all parties and the default buyer is notified under Article 98, and the second declaration of sale is published with all the statements of the first declaration stating this as stipulated in article 98/c.The bidding on the property takes place after the procedure of notifying the sale and according to the first sale and the retarded buyer is obliged to pay the difference between the auction and the last auction, and the previous procedures on the first sale apply to the second sale as work for the text of article 99, and the property may not be disposed of for one year from the date of registration of the property in the name of the last auction and the debtor or his heirs are entitled to recover the property during this period provided that the allowance of the auction, fees and expenses is paid, as stipulated in article 104.

It is clear from the above that there are several procedures to be followed in the event of implementation through the competent enforcement department, and that these procedures are divided into several stages, including with regard to placing the property under the hands of the judiciary, i.e. booking it, then preparing the property for sale, then auctioning the property and fulfilling the creditor's mortgaged right guaranteed by a mortgage bond from the proceeds of the sale.

The procedures for booking the sponsor's property in kind in Jordanian law differ from the procedures for booking the property of the holder, and the basis of this difference is that the sponsor in kind differs from the holder that the property in effect was not owned by the debtor before, so it is not useful to register the alert on the name of the debtor, as no one is likely to deal with the debtor about it, and on the other hand, the application of the procedures for booking the property of the owner of the sponsor in kind leads to the failure to provide protection asIn the case of dealing with the property with the sponsor in kind before registering his warning, the customer will not be able to know before booking the property as he has no means to know about it, and the alert has been recorded on the name of the debtor, as well as in the case of the in-kind sponsor acting on the property to the holder, whoever wants to deal with this holder will not be able before registering the warning of the holder to know that the alert is registered in the name of the debtor, i.e. He will not be able to know the forerunner of the seizure of the property, and finally the expropriation alert by its nature is not merely a prelude to implementation, as in the declaration of the executive bond and the commissioning of the obligation to be directed to the debtor, but rather the beginning of the real estate execution involving the identification of the property in effect, which may only be addressed to the owner of the property to be executed, or who was the owner of it.The property is reserved from the date of registration of the expropriation alert in the name of the in-kind sponsor, and therefore the effects of the seizure in the face of it since then, if the property acts as a registered conduct prior to the registration of the alert, the act shall be in the position of the holder, at which point the creditor must take action against the holder, but if he acts on the property after the de-ownership alert is recorded, this conduct is not carried out in the face of the creditor, and continues to take action against the holder. Implementation completely ignoring this behavior^[2].

The position of the law on the status of immovable funds in order to secure the Jordanian debt:

By referring to the Law on the Placement of Immovable Funds in order to secure Jordanian debt, we can summarize the procedures for implementing the mortgage bond as follows:

The case in question is registered as a mortgage bond and a 30-day notice is sent to the debtor under article 13/1 of the Said Act.After the previous period, the property is seized and valued by three experts in accordance with

article 13/3/a of the Said Act. The debtor is then notified of the hand-holding report and has the right to challenge the report within 10 days before the Court of Appeal, as well as the right of the creditor to object within 10 days, such as the debtor. If the report is not adopted, the chief executive will form another committee of three experts, one of whom will be an employee of the Land Department as a real estate developer, and the report will be a work piece of article 13/3/b of the same law.

Once the hand-holding report has become definitive, the property is placed in public bidding for forty-five days with three consecutive declarations for the duration of each declaration (15) days, and those wishing to enter the bid must be deposited with the Court Fund (10%) of the value provided, and the bid may not start at less than (50%) of the value provided, as confirmed by the text of article 13/3/c of the said law. If the bid allowance is found to be less than (80%) of the estimated value, the bid is extended by a fourth declaration for 15 days and may not be included less than (2%) of the last bid allowance in accordance with a text of article 13/3/D of the said law. According to the researcher, if the bid allowance reaches 80 percent of the estimated value, there is no justification for extending the bid, in short of the long procedures that may be an obstacle to the creditor to obtain his right. In accordance with the above, the Jordanian Court of Cassation ruled that: "Article 13 of the Law on the Placement of Immovable Funds in order to secure debt No. (51) of 1958 and its amendments in the procedures for the implementation of the mortgage bond, states that the fifth paragraph of it was enacted in favour of the person referred to the mortgaged property, so that it must be vacated under the conditions contained in this law, so that the interest it has intended to enter into the budget is not lost, but this right is a right related to it. In particular, it is in person and is not transferred to the person to whom the property is located, nor is this right considered to be a right of ease relating to the property with which it is transferred by virtue of the contract of sale, nor is it a requirement of this contract, which is provided for in the second paragraph of article (202) of the Civil Code, which is determined either by custom or by the nature of the eye subject to the contract, making the privileged claim against it that this right has been transferred to it from the previous owner is incompatible with the law."³¹.

As well as its decision, which states: "If the privileged entity against it is a creditor of the declared bankruptcy entity, and that its debt is guaranteed by a mortgage on two plots of land under a duly regulated debt bond, and since article (12) of the Immovable Funds Status Act in order to secure debt No. 46 of 1952 amended by Law No. 8 of 2001 has given the mortgaged creditor the right to execute the debt bonds regardless of the debtor's case, by requesting the Registration Department to sell the money other than the money. The transferees entail that the debtor shall report this or its legal acting and proceed with the sales proceedings in accordance with the provisions of the law if the required conditions are met regardless of whether the debtor has died or declared bankruptcy and without the creditor being obliged to refer to the estate of the deceased debtor or the bankruptcy applicant' bailiff, and the provisions of the Trade Acts and the placement of immovable funds in order to secure the debt are used as the right of the creditor dependent on the property of execution to fulfil its right without interference. From the bankruptcy agent except in excess of the debt as he is a concessionaire on the mortgaged property and submits to other creditors of the debtor and therefore the bankruptcy judge has no right to stop the sale proceedings on the mortgaged property."

Second: Auction procedures in Iraqi law:

The Iraqi Real Estate Registration Act ⁽⁶¹⁾ included a series of procedures for the auction of the mortgaged property, and these procedures begin after the completion of the transaction of hand-holding the mortgaged property by the head of the department competent to execute, which consists of organizing the list of bidding and announcing the sale of the property, and then the interest of bidding and referring the property to one of the bidders. After the completion of the process of hand-holding the property by the competent head of the department, who organizes a list of the property's bid and the list of the bid, a form in which the descriptions of the property installed in the hand-holding record and the parties to the mortgage contract, mortgage allowance, terms and salary are recorded. We note that the Land Registration Act and the Implementation Law in Iraq do not have a text indicating the need to inform the current debtor and the barrier creditors of the implementation procedures, especially informing them of the bidding list, which is unlike the Jordanian legislator as we have seen before.

However, it should be noted that the Iraqi judiciary went to the need for the justice executor and those involved to sign the bidding list, if it is not signed, it has no legal value, and this is referred to by the Baghdad Court of Appeal as discriminatory, as one of its rulings states: "If the bid list is not signed by the judicial executor and the rest of the stakeholders, as well as no decision by the fair executor to refer the property, in the custody of the bidder, therefore the list of bidding is considered as if it were not in terms of the respect of the executor. This provision has decided to presumption on reporting, i.e. the bidder prepares a judgment amount in this case. It is also noted that the Land Registration Act and the Implementation Act did not specify a certain period of time after the hand-holding treatment to regulate the bidding list, unlike the Jordanian legislator who set this period as we saw at the time.

Thus, the failure to set a certain period after the seizure of the property to organize the bidding list in Iraqi law is a legislative deficiency that must be addressed by the Iraqi legislator by setting a time period after the hand-holding treatment to organize the bidding list, and the Iraqi legislator did not stipulate that the relevant persons (debtor and creditors) should be informed of the list of bids after they have been drawn up. We therefore propose to the Iraqi legislator to amend the wording of article (171/1) of the Land Registration Act. The justice executor may sell more than one property on a single auction list, as article (93/II) of the Iraqi Implementation Act indicates: "If the reserved properties are numerous, the list of auctions of each property shall be regulated separately unless the sole executor decides that it is in the interest to sell more than one property on one list."

In this regard, the Iraqi Court of Cassation ruled that: "... The second paragraph of article (93) of the Enforcement Act was found to have required the regulation of a bid list for each property individually unless the Chief Executive considered it in the interest to sell more than one property with a single bidding list ..." ⁽¹⁸¹⁾.

After the bidding list is organized by the head of the competent department, it is necessary to announce the placement of the property in the bid for 30 days from the day after the date of publication of the announcement'. According to article (171/3) of the Iraqi Land Registration Act and article (96) of the Iraqi Implementation Act, the declaration must include all descriptions of the property, its fixed conditions and its estimated value when it is seized with the names of the creditor and the debtor, their fame, the day of the auction, the time and conditions of annexation and the directorate in which the bidding takes place. The announcement of the status of the property in public bidding must be published in one daily newspaper published in the Department's business area, in the nearest store or in the capital, and a copy of the advertisement must be attached to the department that sells and the advertising period begins from the day after publication'. In one of its rulings, the Iraqi Court of Cassation ruled: "The purpose of the declaration is to notify all in the area where the property is located in the sale, only if it is published in a newspaper written in The Language of The Laté that is spoken and read by the inhabitants of the region in accordance with article VII of the Iraqi Constitution, and this did not happen with regard to the declaration published in Hawkari, a Kurdish political daily ..." ⁽¹¹¹⁾.

After organizing the bidding list and announcing the sale of the property, it is necessary to determine the time at which the bid is opened and to indicate the obligation on those who want to participate in the bid, and to know when the head of the department responsible for the execution of the property decides to refer the definitive and final referral to one of the bidders'.

It should be noted that the Iraqi Land Registration Act required the buyer to provide cash insurance or bank guarantee of at least (10%) of the estimated value of the property, as indicated in article (172/1) of this Act'.

After the publication of the announcement in the newspaper, the bid is open from the day after publication for 30 days, and at 12:00 p.m. on the 30th day, the call to participate in the bidding takes place three times in the competent department, and the bidding takes place in public, and then the head of the department decides to refer the final bidder before the end of the official term, and each annexation is considered not to be increased within five minutes at the end of the bid."If the call is not made three times, it results in the invalidation of the referral decision." In one of its rulings, the Iraqi Court of Cassation ruled that: "The contract is made in the bidding process and the bid falls with a more tender." It should be noted that article (172/4) of the Iraqi Land Registration Act required that in order for the definitive referral to be made to the bidder, the allowance on which the bid was awarded must be at least (80%) of the estimated value of the property, and if the allowance does not reach the said rate, the definitive referral shall not take place, but the bid will be extended for fifteen days with an announcement indicating the amount of fees received on the property, and at the end of the advertising period the definitive referral is made by the amount with which the bid is anchored.

It is clear from the text of article (172/4) of the Land Registration Act that if the allowance does not amount (80%) of the estimated value of the property, the property may not be referred to the bidder in a definitive referral, but the bid must be extended for fifteen days by the end of the bidding, the definitive referral to the bidder, no matter how much the allowance was awarded, and the allowance in which the bid was awarded is likely to be less than (80%) of the estimated value of the property."The land registration law is different from the Iraqi Implementation Act in this provision, in accordance with the provisions of the Law of Implementation if the allowance (80%) of the estimated value does not refer the property to a definitive referral to the last bidder, but the bid must be extended for fifteen days as in the law of real estate registration, but the difference occurs in the case of if the allowance does not reach the result of the second bid (70%) of the estimated value of the property, it may not be referred, but the fair executor decides to reassess the value of the property. The auction was announced again and this is what article (98/II) of the Enforcement Act referred to." According to the researcher, the provision in the Iraqi Implementation Act in article (98/II) is preferable to the provision of article (174/4) of the Land Registration Act because article (98/II) of the Iraqi Implementation Act aims to preserve the prices of real estate and sell it at a higher price than it is in the interest of all parties.

In order to lift the conflict between the two laws, we propose to the Iraqi legislator to amend the wording of article (174) paragraph (4) of the Land Registration Act by referring to article (98/II) of the Iraqi Implementation Act.

If the property is referred to a bidder, the current debtor is informed of the decision to transfer and is required to pay the debt and its accessories with fees and expenses within three days, and when it is completed, the referral becomes final, as indicated by article (173) of the Iraqi Land Registration Act: "The current person is informed of the definitive transfer and is required to pay the debt and its accessories with fees and expenses within three days and upon completion the referral becomes final". Since the execution procedures on the mortgaged property are not only addressed to the current debtor, but also to the owner of the mortgaged property, it is therefore necessary to inform the holder of the decision to transfer the inequity and to ask him to pay the debt and its accessories and all fees and expenses within a period of three days, and if he does not do so, the property shall be registered in the name of the shop owner. If the mortgaged property is referred to a bidder in a final referral and pays the legal allowance and fees, the property is registered in its name, as indicated by article (181/1) of the Land Registration Act, stating: "The property shall be registered in the name of the buyer or full-time after payment of the legal allowance and fees".

However, what is the ruling if the registration of the property in the name of the referred person is delayed and the delay is more than 30 days from the date of payment of the allowance and fees? In this case, the person referred to the property has the right to a final referral to request the avoidance of the bid if the registration of the property in his name is delayed by more than 30 days from the date of payment of the allowance and fees, provided that the registration delay is not due to the property being referred to him as a final referral and the decision¹⁰ annul the property is issued by the Head of the Department. This is stipulated in article (181/4) of the Iraqi Land Registration Act: "A person who has referred the property under his custody has the right to a final referral to request the avoidance of the bid if the registration of the sale in his name is delayed by more than thirty days from the date of payment of the allowance and fees, provided that the delay is not due to it by the decision of the head of the department," which is the same provision in article (104) of the Iraqi Implementation Act.

It is clear to the researcher through the advanced text that there are conditions that must be met so that the shop keeper can request the avoidance of the bid and these conditions are:

1. Pay the allowance and real estate registration fees and delay the registration of the property in its name for more than thirty days from the date it pays the allowance and fees.
2. The delay in registering in the name of the shop keeper should be due to a reason in which the referral is not entitled, as if the registration was delayed due to the failure to find the property register or a person's claim to ownership of the property sold, establishing a due claim and obtaining a decision to delay the registration of the property sold in the buyer's name, but if the registration delay is due to the reason for the shop's property as if it did not provide the documents required for registration, in this case it is not entitled to request the avoidance of the bid as well as if it pays the allowance and fees.
3. The decision to cancel the bid shall be issued by the head of the department if the sale takes place in the Real Estate Registration Department, and by the chief executive if the sale takes place in the execution department.

The second requirement

Legal status of the holder in the event of expropriation of the mortgaged property

First: The legal status of the holder before registering the decision to anchor the auction:

Auction proceedings would not affect the legal status of the mortgaged property holder before the auction decision is registered, as he remains the owner of the mortgaged property until the auction is registered. "However, the owner's ownership in this period is restricted, and the reason for this restriction is due to the attachment of creditors dependent on the mortgaged property owned by the holder." In the light of this restriction of ownership of the holder, the question arises as to the provision of the fruits generated from the mortgaged property, whether it is owned by the holder or is the right of the mortgaged creditors to do so, and what is the provision of destruction or damage to the mortgaged property? Can the holder arrange in kind the mortgaged property in this period?

The Jordanian legislator in article (1360) required a civilian to refund the proceeds of the mortgaged property from the date of his warning of debt payment by the mortgaged creditor, while the Jordanian Implementation Act obliged the holder to refund the related appendages that occurred in the sale after the date of the hand-holding.^[21] Since the Jordanian Civil Code is a general law and the law of implementation is a special law, part of the jurisprudence has argued that the provisions of the Jordanian Implementation Act concerning the fruits of the mortgaged property must be adopted.^[22]

The Iraqi Civil Code did not contain an explicit provision specifying when the fruits would be attached to the mortgaged property and that the mortgaged creditors had the right to reap the mortgaged property, and it could be argued that the right of the holder to reap the mortgaged property would end when the mortgaged creditor would be warned to pay the mortgaged debt. From that date, the fruits would be attached to the mortgaged property and the mortgaged creditors would be entitled to it, and in the absence of an explicit provision specifying when the fruits would join the mortgaged property, we therefore propose to the Iraqi legislator to add a text to civil law. The Iraqi is similar to the text of article (1360/2) of a Jordanian civilian.

We note that The Jordanian Civil Code makes the holder responsible for any sabotage or defect that occurs in the mortgaged property, as article (1360/1) refers to: "1- The holder guarantees all sabotage or defects that affect the property." The wisdom is that the holder is the owner of the mortgaged property before registering the decision to anchor the auction, and therefore has the right to use all powers over it but without any promise that may result in its destruction, damage or relock. The Iraqi Civil Code did not contain a provision establishing the holder's responsibility for the loss or damage to the mortgaged property, if the destruction or damage was caused by it, which is undoubtedly a legislative deficiency that must be addressed by an explicit provision establishing the holder's responsibility for destruction or damage if it occurs in the case of the Jordanian legislator, and we propose to add a text similar to article (1360/1) of a Jordanian civilian. The burden of establishing the holder's liability for loss or damage lies with the mortgaged creditors who claim that the mortgaged property has been destroyed or damaged. The holder is not asked about the loss or damage to the mortgaged property due to a foreigner, force majeure, force or normal use of the mortgaged property, as if death or damage occurred due to another person, flooding, earthquake or any other reason that has nothing to do with the will of the holder. With regard to the authority of the holder to dispose of the mortgaged property, the mortgage does not restrict this authority and the holder can dispose of the mortgaged property and this conduct is correct as long as it does not affect the mortgaged creditor's right. The holder can sell, trade or give the mortgaged property, all of which are valid but the property is transferred in charge of the mortgage.

The authority of the holder to dispose of the mortgaged property shall only be complied with from the date of the decision to seize the property, and after the decision to seize the property may not be made without the consent of the authority that placed the reservation on his record, and article (86/2) of the Iraqi Enforcement Act stipulates that: "No transaction may be made on the property after the booking signal has been placed without the approval of the Directorate of Execution, which placed the booking."

With regard to the right of the holder to arrange rights in kind on the mortgaged property, it is noted that all mortgages decided by the holder between acquisition of ownership and registration of the auction judgment are valid, but their rank follows that of the creditors of the former owners of the property whose rights are registered, as well as the rights of ease, use and housing are considered valid but not executed against the mortgaged creditor, as the property is sold as free of it.

Second: The legal status of the holder after the registration of the decision to anchor the auction:

The legal status of the holder varies at the stage of auctioning the mortgaged property and anchoring the auction on the auction, and the auction here may be the holder himself, and may be third parties, so it is necessary to indicate the implications of the auction of the holder and its anchorage, and it is necessary to indicate the right of the holder to refer to the previous owner or debtor.

2- Anchoring the auction to third parties (not winning)

The auction may be based on the non-holder, whether it is the creditor requesting the sale, another creditor or a foreign debt and mortgaged property, in which case the auctioneer is obliged to pay the price at which the auction was based, as well as the expenses spent by the holder of his title deed and in the registration of this bond and the advertisements he made as well as the expenses required by the clearance procedures, which the applicant may have accelerated, if the price at which the auction was awarded Higher than the amount offered by the holder^[1]. The auction of the non-holder entails the transfer of ownership of the mortgaged property to the auction holder and the purge of the rights restricted to it. Article 1359 of a Jordanian civilian states: "If the auction of the mortgaged property is established as an insurance mortgage on the non-holder, it earns it under the decision to anchor the auction and receives its right from the holder." This is stated in article (1313/2) by an Iraqi civilian: "If the bid is based on a person other than the holder, whether the holder enters the bid or not, the one who has been awarded the bid receives his right from the holder under the awarding provision." It is the holder who transfers the property to the auctioneer with several consequences, as the owner's freedom to dispose of the mortgaged property is restricted despite being his owner as of the registration of the reservation decision in the Land Registry and his actions on the property from this registration are not effective against the two barriers:

It should be noted that the seller of the mortgaged property is the holder and that the buyer is the person on whom the bid was based, and that the bond is the basis of the auction, which, of course, does not transfer ownership between the seller and the buyer or to third parties except from the date of registration, either for the property or the transfer at which the disposal is subject to registration procedures, and in this sense the Iraqi Court of Cassation ruled in one of its decisions that: "The sale of the vehicle in the ongoing public auction from the official departments makes the buyer its owner after taking into account the registration procedures in the competent traffic departments"^[3] and therefore it is necessary to register the award of the auction to transfer the property from the holder to the auctioneer, and the holder remains the owner of the property.

As long as this provision is not recorded, the following follows:

First, in terms of the price at which the auction was awarded, it is considered the property of the holder from which the creditors will meet their rights and what remains of it and the creditors who are dependent on it, and the bet has no right to increase..

Second: In terms of fruits: the fruits of the holder because they are generated by his king, and the follower continues, that this rule is disrupted by the warning of the holder of the debt on the property, as from this date the fruits join the reserved property, and become reserved like him, and as such stipulated Article (1360/2) jordanian civilian says: "Therefore, the yield of the property must be refunded from the date of its warning of the death of the debt." This is the right of creditors and the holder has been responsible for it to them ever since'.

Third: The owner does not ask about the damage he has caused to the mortgaged property during his ownership, because the owner does not ask what is being damaged from his money, but because this money may be attached to the right of the mortgaged creditors, the owner must refrain from destroying it in the interest of the creditors. The compensation paid by the holder in this case is attached to the price of the mortgaged property, and is distributed to creditors at their own rate, with the holder having to return to the former owner on the grounds of guarantee and recover from it what he paid to the mortgagee as compensation'.

Fourth: The transfer of the property is disinfectant from the holder to the auction holder: the registration of the decision to establish the auction results in the cleansing of the property sold from the rights of the concession, the insurance mortgage and the bio-mortgage, which informs the owners of the deposit of the terms of sale, and their right to the price is transferred, and therefore the purge does not respond to the original rights in kind. The property moves heavily on these rights to the auction holder, these rights when they are in force against the mortgaged creditors are effective against the auction holder, and they are so when they are the same when they are in force. It has been acquired prior to foreclosure, and the effect of the purge is limited to the dependent rights of the property, whether determined by law such as concession rights or by judicial right as jurisdiction, or by agreement such as the insurance and biomeal mortgage contract, and we note that the provisions of the Egyptian Civil Code mention the biomeal mortgage among the consequential in-kind rights from which the property is cleared in the event of forced sale'.

Fifth: The auction does not cleanse the property of the rights that the holder had before it owned it. The owner of the property that was expropriated may have original or consequential in-kind rights, before the property is transferred to it, and these rights are usually with the owner's property while in possession, or remain suspended, as a person may not have such rights over his property, as long as they are originally decided and necessarily continued on the property of others, but what is their fate at the time of transfer? New and followed by its former owner? Jordan's Civil Code did not provide a provision for such a return, and if it did so, it would not have enriched creditors at the expense of the holder, and in our view those rights should be returned despite the silence of the text;

The right of the holder to refer to the former owner or debtor:

Having indicated the implications of exercising the right of traceability against the holder, the law has guaranteed the holder the right of return, whether on the previous owner or on the debtor, if he or she suffers a loss due to the direct tracking in the face of it, and therefore must distinguish between the return of the previous owner or the debtor:

A. Return of the previous owner:

The former owner means the person from whom the owner received the mortgaged property such as the seller and the donor, and the claim under which the holder returns the previous owner is the claim of guarantee of entitlement, and if the former owner is a seller the provisions of article (505) are applied jordanian civilian and article (554) civil Iraqi on the guarantee of the benefit of the sale, but if it is a donor, the provisions of article (568) apply to a Jordanian civilian and article (614) an Iraqi civilian relating to the guarantee of the benefit of the gifted person, under which the donor is a guarantor only if the reason for the entitlement is deliberately concealed, but if The gift was mosquitoes, ensuring the entitlement only as much as the gifted (winner) performed from Awad.

B. Return of the debtor:

The holder may also return the debtor for the claim of enrichment for no reason^[9] for what he paid more than he had under his title deed and replace creditors who undersought their rights and, in particular, replace them with insurance provided by the debtor without insurance provided by a person other than the debtor'. It follows that if the creditor who has fulfilled his debt from the price of the property dispossessed has another mortgage or another in-kind insurance provided to him by the debtor, the holder replaces him in this insurance and returns to the debtor on the pretext of solutions, but if the one who provided the insurance is a sponsor in kind, the holder does not have the right to refer to it under the pretext of solutions, nor can the holder refer to the personal sponsor of the debtor, and the wisdom of not authorizing the right of return to the sponsor personally or in kind, even if it is in kind. Under the pretext of replacing the creditor, the mortgaged property would not have been transferred to the debtor, the debtor would not have returned the sponsor simply for the debtor to dispose of the property to the holder'.

Conclusion

1. The Iraqi legislator did not provide for a penalty for violating the procedures for the liberation of the property or judging if there was a material error.
2. The Iraqi legislator did not specify a certain period of time, as the Jordanian legislator did, after the hand-holding treatment to organize the bidding list so that the mortgaged property should not be prolonged, nor did it provide for the need to inform the relevant parties, i.e. the current debtor, the barrier creditors and the holder.
3. The Iraqi legislator, as the Jordanian legislator did, did not provide for the provision of the fruits inflicted on the mortgaged property, nor did it address the issue of the destruction or damage to the mortgaged drug, contrary to the position of the Jordanian legislator who organized the issue.
4. The Jordanian legislator and the Iraqi legislator did not address the legal status of the mortgaged property holder in relation to the rights that the holder of this property may have in kind before the property is transferred to it, especially in the case of expropriation of the property from the holder and the auction of third parties.

Recommendations

1. The Iraqi legislator should deal with the penalty for violating the procedures for the liberation of the mortgaged property in article (1308/2) by arranging for the mortgaged creditor who had been wrongly or underreported to the mortgaged creditor and would have harmed him.
2. The Iraqi legislator should set a period of time after hand-holding treatment to organize the bidding list so as not to prolong the period on the reservation of the mortgaged property, so we propose to reformulate the text of article (171/1) of the Iraqi Registration Act, so that this list is regulated within seven days of the date of the hand-holding.
3. With regard to the auction of the non-holder, we propose to Jordanian and Iraqi legislators the need to provide for the return of the rights in kind that the holder had acquired prior to the transfer of ownership of the mortgaged property to him.

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- See: Article (1361) is a Jordanian civilian, and the Jordanian legislator has absolutely stated this provision, i.e. if the bid is settled on the holder or others, and article (1314) is an Iraqi civilian.
- Abdul Razzaq al-Sanhouri, C10, former reference, p. 605.
- Dr. Abdul Majid al-Hakim and others, former reference, p. 155.
- Mohammed WahiduddinSwar, former reference, p. 124.
- Nabil Ibrahim Saad, former reference, p. 167.

See: Article (293 to 295) Jordanian civilians, and Article (243) Iraqi civilians.
Ali Hadi al-Obaidi, former reference, p. 294.

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